

GUANYLALKYLUREAS AND THEIR METALLIC COMPLEXES. PART VI COBALT(III) COMPLEXES

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The preparation and properties of the complex compounds of cobalt(III) with a number of guanylalkylureas comprising guanyl-*N*¹-methyl-, -ethyl-, -butylⁿ-, -butylⁱ-, -amylⁱ-, and -hexylⁿ-ureas have been described. The complex cobalt(III)-*tris*-guanyl-*N*¹-alkylurea base and its salts are red to rose-red in colour. The conductances of some of their chloride in aqueous solution agree with the composition of tri-univalent electrolyte. All these complexes have been found to be diamagnetic and, hence, belong to the inner-level octahedral type with *d*²*sp*³ hybrid covalent bonds.

The action of KCN on the cobalt(III)-*tris*-guanyl-*N*¹-methyl- or -ethylurea base and its salts has also been studied. This has led to the isolation of dicyano-cobalt(III)-*bis*-guanyl-*N*¹-methyl- or -ethylurea base. These may be represented by [Co (R-GauH) (R-Gau) (CN)₂], where R=Me or Et.

The preparation and properties of copper, nickel and palladium complexes with guanylalkylureas have been described previously (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 567; 576; 1960, 37, 499). Ray and Bandopadhyay (*ibid.*, 1952, 29, 865) have described the preparation and properties of the cobalt(III) complexes of unsubstituted guanylurea and *N*⁶-phenylguanylurea. The cobalt(III) complexes of the guanyl-*N*¹-alkylureas have not been studied so far, and the present work records an account of the preparation and properties of the same with some of the guanyl-*N*¹-alkylureas which comprise guanyl-*N*¹-methyl-, -ethyl-, -butylⁿ-, -butylⁱ-, -amylⁱ-, and -hexylⁿ-ureas. The compounds can be represented as :

I. [Co (R-GauH)₃] X₃. *n*H₂O, where R-GauH=one molecule of guanyl -*N*¹- alkylurea and X=Cl or $\frac{1}{2}$ SO₄; R=methyl, ethyl, butylⁿ, butylⁱ, amylⁱ, and hexylⁿ unit. These compounds are either dull red or rose-red in colour.

With the exception of cobalt(III)-*tris*-guanyl-*N*¹-hexylⁿ-urea sulphate, which is insoluble in water, the other complex cobalt(III)-guanyl-*N*¹-alkylurea sulphates are soluble in water but insoluble in ethanol and acetone.

The complex cobalt(III)-guanyl-*N*¹-alkylurea chlorides are extremely soluble in water and ethanol but insoluble in acetone. The solubility of the complex chloride decreases with increase in the chain length of the substituent. A strong solution of the complex chloride has been found to give characteristic precipitates with heavier anions like dithionate, chromate, phosphate, etc. and also with many complex anions.

The conductance measurement of the complex cobalt(III)-*tris*-guanyl-*N*¹-methyl-, -ethyl-, and -butylⁱ-urea chlorides in solution furnishes values, which agree with those for a tri-univalent electrolyte in composition. The variation of Δ_{∞} values calculated from Δ_v values by Walden's formula indicates that the cobalt(III) complexes undergo partial hydrolysis in dilute solution.

II. [Co (R-Gau)₃]. *n*H₂O, where R-GauH = R - NH - C(=O) - NH - C(=O) - NH₂

The solubility of these dark red complex bases in water also decreases with increase in the chain length of the substituent, whereas that in ethanol and acetone increases. The complex bases are usually hygroscopic in nature and absorb CO₂ from the air. They liberate ammonia from the ammonium salts and form the corresponding complex salts. On heating to 90°, the compounds lose their water and form anhydrous bases.

By treating the solution or aqueous suspension of the complex cobalt(III)-guanyl N^2 -methyl- or -ethylurea base or their salt with potassium cyanide, either in the cold or at the temperature of the water bath, yellow complex dicyano-cobalt(III)-bis-guanyl- N^2 -methyl- or -ethylurea base (anhydro-base), similar to those of the dicyano-cobalt(III)-bis-biguanide or substituted biguanide complexes (Sengupta and Rây, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 201), are formed. These can be formulated as $[\text{Co}(\text{R-GauH})(\text{R-Gau})(\text{CN})_2]$; $\text{R}=\text{Me}$ or Et . These are very sparingly soluble in water and suffer decomposition easily on boiling with water and also with acids, but are stable towards alkali solutions. The solid compounds decompose on heating to 90° . The aqueous suspension on treatment with a strong solution of ammonium salts slowly decomposes and the corresponding salts of the complex bases could not therefore be isolated in the pure state. The dicyano-cobalt(III)-bis-guanyl- N^2 -methyl- and -ethylurea bases are less stable and more soluble than those of the methyl- and ethylbiguanide complexes (Sengupta and Rây, *loc. cit.*) though there is a close resemblance between them in other respects; hence the structure of the dicyano-cobalt(III)-bis-guanyl- N^2 -methyl- or -ethylurea base (anhydro-base) can be represented by the following configuration:

(where $\text{R} = \text{Me}$ or Et)

The action of KCN on cobalt(III)-tris-guanyl- N^2 -alkylurea ($\text{R}=\text{Bu}^n, \text{Bu}^i, \text{Am}^i$ and hexylⁿ) results in the formation of the corresponding dicyano complexes in a rather impure state, from which the pure products could not be isolated.

The guanylalkylureas form with cobalt(II) salts in alkaline solution yellow precipitates of the complex cobalt(II)-guanyl- N^2 -alkylureas, which oxidise to the cobalt(III) state. The complex cobalt(III)-tris-guanyl- N^2 -alkylureas are all diamagnetic; hence they belong to the type of inner metallic penetration complexes with octahedral d^2sp^3 hybrid bonds.

Cobalt(III)-tris-guanyl- N^2 -alkylurea complexes closely resemble the cobalt(III)-tris-biguanide and tris-alkylbiguanide complexes (Rây and Dutt, this *Journal*, 1959, 16, 621; Dutta, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1959, 302, 237; Sengupta, unpublished work; Ray, unpublished work) in their composition and also in their physical and chemical properties. The colour of the cobalt(III)-tris-guanyl- N^2 -alkylurea complexes corresponds to those of its biguanide and alkylbiguanide complexes, except that the latter are more brightly coloured. The solubility of the two series runs in a parallel course, the biguanide complex being less soluble. The two series are more or less stable towards acids or alkalis, and have the same absorption maxima (480-485 $\text{m}\mu$; $\epsilon_{\text{Co-bis}}$ 231.5; $\epsilon_{\text{Co-tris}}$ 201.7). The cobalt(III)-biguanide and alkylbiguanide complexes are generally

Base : {Found : Co, 13.02; N, 37.00; H₂O (by loss at 90°), 2.12. [Co (C₂H₅ Gau)₃] 0.5H₂O requires Co, 12.97; N, 36.93; H₂O, 1.98%}.

Chloride : {Found : Co, 9.32; N, 26.22; Cl 16.76; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 13.84. [Co (C₂H₅ GauH)₃]Cl₃.5H₂O requires Co, 9.14; N, 26.02; Cl, 16.50; H₂O, 14.09%}.

C. Cobalt (III)-tris-guanyl-N¹-butylⁿurea

Base : (i). CoSO₄.7H₂O (1.5 g.) in water (20 c.c.) and guanyl-N¹-butylⁿurea sulphate (6g.) in 50 c.c. of water were mixed together and to the mixture 5*N* alkali was added dropwise till it was strongly alkaline. To this mixture containing a yellow precipitate of cobalt (II) complex 10-15 c.c. of H₂O₂ was added with constant stirring. The resulting mixture was warmed on a water bath for about half an hour when a dark red oil collected at the bottom. The mother liquor was decanted and the oil was washed with water. Finally, the oil was treated with ice-cold water and stirred thoroughly when it began to solidify. This was filtered, washed with water, and then recrystallised from acetone. The red compound was dried over CaCl₂ and KOH.

(ii). The same compound was also obtained in a pure state by the interaction of cobalt (III) hexammine chloride and alkaline guanyl-N¹-butylⁿurea sulphate at the temperature of water bath, when a dark red oil separated, from which the pure compound was obtained as described in the previous method. {Found : Co, 11.26; N, 31.03. [Co (C₄H₉Gau)₃] requires Co, 11.14; N, 31.07%}.

The *complex sulphate* was obtained by neutralising the ethanolic solution of the complex base with H₂SO₄ (dil.). The product was filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried in air. It is fairly soluble in water but insoluble in ethanol and acetone. {Found : Co, 8.63; N, 24.04; SO₄, 20.90; H₂O (by loss at 100°), 3.87. [Co (C₄H₉ GauH)₃] (SO₄)₃.3H₂O requires Co, 8.38; N, 23.86; SO₄, 20.45; H₂O, 3.83%}. $\chi_g = -0.069 \times 10^{-6}$.

In a similar manner the cobalt (III)-tris-guanyl-N¹-butylⁿ-, -amylⁿ- and -hexylⁿurea complexes were prepared and their properties studied.

D. Cobalt (III)-tris-guanyl-N¹-butylⁿurea

Base : {Found : Co, 10.91; N, 30.31; H₂O (by loss at 90°), 3.01. [Co (C₄H₉ Gau)₃]H₂O requires Co, 10.75; N, 30.65; H₂O, 3.28%}.

Sulphate : {Found : Co, 7.43; N, 24.01; SO₄, 18.31; H₂O (by loss at 100°), 14.75. [Co (C₄H₉ GauH)₃] (SO₄)₃.13.5H₂O requires Co, 7.39; N, 24.07; SO₄, 18.04; H₂O, 14.84%}. $\chi_g = -0.059 \times 10^{-6}$.

The *chloride* was prepared by neutralising the acetone solution of the complex base with HCl (dil.). {Found : Co, 8.92; N, 25.62; Cl, 15.79; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 4.32. [Co (C₄H₉ GauH)₃]Cl₃ requires Co, 8.87; N, 25.24; Cl, 16.01; H₂O, 4.06%}.

E. Cobalt (III)-tris-guanyl-N¹-amylⁿurea

Base : {Found : Co, 9.95; N, 28.56; H₂O (by loss at 90°) 1.71. [Co (C₅H₁₁ Gau)₃] 0.5H₂O requires Co, 10.16; N, 28.91; H₂O, 1.55%}.

F. Cobalt (III)-tris-guanyl-N¹-hexylⁿurea

Base : {Found : Co, 8.86; N, 26.01; H₂O (by loss at 90°), 5.74. [Co (C₆H₁₃ Gau)₃] 2H₂O requires Co, 9.07; N, 25.84; H₂O, 5.54%}.

Sulphate: {Found: Co, 6.97; N, 19.10; SO₄, 16.37. [Co (C₆H₁₃ GauH)₃]₂(SO₄)₃ · 12H₂O requires Co, 6.81; N, 19.40; SO₄, 16.62%}. The complex sulphate decomposes on heating to 80°.

TABLE I
Conductance of cobalt (III)-tris-guanylalkylurea chloride.

Temp. = 35° ± 1°.

<i>v</i> (litres)	N/32	N/64	N/128	N/256	N/512	N/1024	} Δ_{∞} = 128.6. Molar conductivity = 385.8
Δ_v (methyl)	93.07	90.18	101.12	110.8	125.7	139.6	
Δ_{∞}	127.2	113.6	119.8	124.9	137.3	148.7	
Δ_v (ethyl)	..	..	81.30	95.41	107.0	130.5	} Δ_{∞} = 114.9. Molar conductivity = 344.7
Δ_{∞}	..	..	96.36	107.8	116.8	138.8	
Δ_v (butyl)	..	86.28	104.7	116.3	125.7	141.5	} Δ_{∞} = 130.4. Molar conductivity = 391.2
Δ_{∞}	..	108.7	123.0	131.4	137.2	150.7	

$\Delta_{\infty} = \Delta_v (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 n_2 \cdot v^{-1})$ (Walden's formula), where n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the cations and anions respectively, and ' v ' indicates dilution in litres.

Dicyano-cobalt (III)-bis-guanyl-N¹-methyl- and-ethylurea Complexes

To a concentrated solution of cobalt (III)-tris-guanyl-N¹-methyl (and ethyl) urea base or its salts a strong solution of KCN was added, and the resulting solution was warmed on a water bath for a short period till the orange-red solution assumed a golden yellow colour. This was then kept in a desiccator containing CaCl₂ and KOH, where yellow crystals of the dicyano complex separated slowly. In the case of guanyl-N¹-ethylurea complex the crystals appeared after a long time (5-7 days) and the yield was very poor. The products were filtered, washed first thoroughly with water, then with ethanol, and finally dried over CaCl₂ and KOH.

Dicyano-cobalt (III)-bis-guanyl-N¹-methylurea (anhydro-base): {Found: Co, 17.42; N (total), 41.02. [Co (CH₃-C₂N₄H₅)₂ (CH₃-C₂N₄H₄)₂ (CN)₂] requires Co, 17.36; N, 41.18%}.

Dicyano-cobalt (III)-bis-guanyl-N¹-ethylurea (anhydro-base): {Found: Co, 16.12; N (total), 37.45. [Co (C₂H₅-C₂N₄H₅) (C₂H₅-C₂N₄H₄)₂ (CN)₂] requires Co, 15.95; N, 37.84%}.

Methods of Analysis

Cobalt in the complex was estimated as CoSO₄ after ignition with strong H₂SO₄. Nitrogen was estimated as usual by Kjeldahl's method, and the anions by the usual standard procedure.

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